

Antibody Characterization Report for ACSL5 (Long-chain-fatty-acid--CoA ligase 5)

YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

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Target:

Protein name used in this report: ACSL5

Recommended protein name: Long-chain-fatty-acid--CoA ligase 5

Gene name: ACSL5

Uniprot: Q9ULC5

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science [1]. In this study, we characterized eight ACSL5 commercial antibodies for western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using a standardized experimental protocol [2] based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. We identified many well-performing antibodies and encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibody for their specific needs. HCT 116 was selected based on evidence of appropriate ACSL5 protein expression determined through DepMap [3, 4]. HCT 116 was modified with CRISPR/Cas9 to knockout the corresponding *ACSL5* gene.

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
ATCC	CCL-247	CVCL_0291	HCT 116	WT
Structural Genomics Consortium	-	-	HCT 116	ACSL5 KO

Table 2: Summary of the ACSL5 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µl)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab188507	1076458-1	AB_3086621	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.33	Wb
Abnova	H00051703-B01P	10133	AB_10630998	polyclonal	-	mouse	0.50	Wb
Abnova	H00051703-M01*	1B081-5H8	AB_509241	monoclonal	5H8	mouse	0.50	Wb, IP
Bio-Techne	NB100-2918	P1	AB_789824	polyclonal	-	goat	0.50	Wb
Bio-Techne	NBP1-59645	QC17535-190314	AB_11031095	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Proteintech	15708-1-AP	00024707	AB_2257881	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.35	Wb, IP
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-24595*	YI4059331	AB_2637210	monoclonal	CL0275	mouse	1.00	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-52392	YI4059337A	AB_2637624	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.10	Wb, IF

Wb=western blot, IP= immunoprecipitation, IF=immunofluorescence, *=monoclonal antibody

Materials and methods

Antibodies

All the ACSL5 antibodies tested are listed in Table 2. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 65-6120 and 62-6520). Peroxidase-conjugated donkey anti-goat is from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A15999). Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse secondary antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A21429 and A21424). Alexa-555-conjugated donkey anti-goat secondary antibody is from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A-21432).

CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing

Cell lines used are listed in Table 1. HCT 116 ACSL5 KO clone was generated with low passage cells using a previously published protocol [4]. Two guide RNAs were used to knockout the ACSL5 gene (sequence guide 1: CACCGCCTTAACAGGATCTACGATA, sequence guide 2: AAACATATCGTAGATCCTGTTAAGGC).

Cell culture

Cells were cultured in DMEM high glucose (GE Healthcare cat. number SH30081.01) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 2 mM L-glutamine (Wisent cat. number 609-065), 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent cat. number 450201).

Antibody screening by western blot

Western blots were performed as described in our standard operating procedure [5]. HCT 116 WT and ACSL5 KO (listed in Table 1) were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder from GeneDireX (cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer from Bio-Rad (cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on

the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) from Cell Signaling (cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Immunoprecipitation was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [6]. Antibody-beads conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with with 30µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse and goat antibodies) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 hr at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

HCT 116 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2.0 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 hr at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP lysis buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels. Anti-mouse IgG for IP:HRP (Abcam, cat. number ab131368) was used as a secondary detection system at a concentration of 2 µg/ml.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

Immunofluorescence was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [7]. HCT 116 WT and *ACSL5* KO were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively. The fluorescent dyes used are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number C2925 and C34565). WT and KO cells were plated in a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom. (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator. Cells were fixed in 4% PFA (in PBS) for 15 min at room temperature and then washed 3 times with PBS. Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 for 10 min

at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5% BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary ACSL5 antibodies O/N at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibodies in IF buffer at a dilution of 1.0 µg/ml for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and once with PBS.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro confocal high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.95 water immersion objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa-555 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 x 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification. Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

Figure 1: ACSL5 antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: ACSL5 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 3: ACSL5 antibody screening by immunofluorescence

Figure 1: ACSL5 antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of HCT 116 WT and ACSL5 KO were prepared, and 40 µg of protein were processed for Western blot with the indicated ACSL5 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. Antibody dilution used: ab188507 at 1/1000, H00051703-B01P at 1/1000, H00051703-M01* at 1/1000, NB100-2918 at 1/1000, NBP1-59645 at 1/200, 15708-1-AP at 1/1000, MA5-24595* at 1/200, PA5-52392 at 1/500. Predicted band size: 76 kDa. *=monoclonal antibody

Figure 2: ACSL5 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

HCT 116 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 2.0 µg of the indicated ACSL5 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the indicated ACSL5 antibody. For western blot, MA5-24595* was used at 1/200. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate; HC=antibody heavy chain. *=monoclonal antibody

Figure 3: ACSL5 antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

HCT 116 WT and ACSL5 KO cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio in a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom. Cells were stained with the indicated ACSL5 antibodies and with the corresponding Alexa-fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (identification of WT cells), red (antibody staining) and far-red (identification of KO cells) channels was performed. Representative images of the blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. Antibody dilution used: ab188507 at 1/150, H00051703-B01P at 1/1250, H00051703-M01* at 1/500, NB100-2918 at 1/500, NBP1-59645 at 1/250, 15708-1-AP at 1/150, MA5-24595* at 1/100, PA5-52392 at 1/100. Bars = 10 µm. *=monoclonal antibody

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